

LATEX OF SOME INDIGENOUS RUBBER YIELDING PLANTS. PART I. *EXCAECARIA AGALLOCHA*, LINN

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The latex of *Excaecaria agallocha* has been shown to contain a fat, resin esters; resenes, rubber proteins, crude fibre and inorganic matter. The fat consists of the glycerides of lignoceric, cerotic, oleic and linoleic acids.

Due to the present shortage of rubber in India an urgency has arisen to discover additional sources of this vital product necessitating the investigation of plant latices which may prove alternatives to *Hevea* rubber. In other countries similar attempts have been made, with the result that United States of America has started the cultivation of *Parthenium argentatum* (the Mexican plant Guayule, with 20% of rubber content. *Anon.*, 1942, *Chronica Botanica*, 7, (3) 138) and the United States of Soviet Russia is obtaining her demand of rubber from a species of dandelion (*Taraxacum tau-saghyz*), which is reported to be grown extensively in South Uzbekistan. In Australia intensive efforts are being made to extend the cultivation of the naturalized vine *Cryptostegia grandiflora* whose latex has been found to yield rubber as high as 23% (unpublished data by one of the authors). Even though the yield of rubber from these plants is not as high as from *Hevea* their cultivation etc. is being encouraged with a view to making the country not wholly dependent on foreign supplies.

No serious attempt appears to have been made in India to properly investigate the latices of indigenous plants which occur all over the country. Some of these, especially those belonging to the families, *Apocynaceae*, *Asclepiadaceae*, *Euphorbiaceae*, *Compositae* and *Urticaceae*, yield latices which contain rubber. Any of these may turn out to be a rich source of rubber but unfortunately the information on the yield of latex and its rubber content is not available. It is for this reason that the present investigation has been started and it is proposed to examine only those plants which are known to occur in abundance. One such plant is *Excaecaria agallocha* which covers nearly 400 sq. miles in Sundarbans and of which nearly 300,000 trees per annum could be made available for the tapping of latex.

Generally speaking, latices contain resin and caoutchouc and that latices from different species of trees are different in character even in closely related species. Some contain high proportion of caoutchouc and lower proportion of resin and proteins, whilst the majority contain higher proportion of resin which are intimately associated with caoutchouc, yielding rubber of poorer quality. Those with a high proportion of resin or resin like substances are, in normal times, of small value for rubber although they may be useful for other purposes. From the commercial point of view, however, this association with high proportion of resin is undesirable and unsuitable for the extraction of rubber. *Hevea* latex, for example, contains about 36.0% of caoutchouc, 2.0% resin and 2.0% of proteins, whereas the latex from *Calotropis procera* contains about 2.0% rubber, and 20 per cent. of resin and proteins, making it unsuitable as the source of rubber. In the present emergency, however, any latex that contains a reasonable amount of rubber is of value and should be investigated.

Hevea, as it is known to-day, is the result of intensive cultural operations and developments and should not therefore be taken as standard for its rubber content when comparing the plants which grow in wild state. It is possible to improve the rubber content of wild plants also, with cultivation and selection of proper strains. This, however, is a long term research and

not likely to yield results of value during the present urgency, but the same urgency demands that all possible sources should be examined even though the rubber content may not be as high as in *Hevea*.

Excaecaria agallocha, Linn., Vern. *gewa* (Bengal), is a small evergreen bushy tree of the coastal and tidal forests. It is very common in Sundarbans and also occurs in the deltas of the Godavari and the Kistna. When a sharp cut is made on its bark a quantity of an acrid milky juice flows down which on drying hardens to a black caoutchouc-like material. One set of cuts gives milk for only a minute or two and then a fresh cut has to be made when again the juice flows copiously and ceases after a couple of minutes.

The latex was obtained through the courtesy of the Divisional Forest Officer, Sundarbans, who had sent the material in sealed tins without the addition of ammonia. The chemical examination showed it to contain only 2.7% of rubber, which quantity is obviously too low for commercial extraction. The results of the chemical examination of this latex do not appear to have been recorded before and are, therefore, being reported now. The method adopted for the separation and isolation of the various constituents of this latex is in general the same as recommended for para rubber latex (Davis and Sadler, Allen's Commercial Organic Analysis, 4th Ed. Vol. 3, p. 106). It had, however, to be modified in the present case to separate the fatty oil and resin esters from the resenes occurring in the latex.

EXPERIMENTAL

The latex had the following characteristics :—

Colour	Light yellow	Odour	repulsive	Specific gravity at 28°	0.9723
Acid value	40	Steam volatile matter	nil	Water solubles	4.0%
Coagulated matter	34.0%	Total solids	38.0%	Ash	1.7%

500 G. of the latex were diluted with water to a litre and coagulated with the addition of 5 c.c. of glacial acetic acid at 80°. The precipitate was allowed to settle and the supernatant liquid decanted. The residue was stirred with hot water, the solids again allowed to settle and the supernatant liquid decanted. This operation was repeated a few times after which the thick slurry of the coagulated matter was centrifuged to remove most of the water. It was then dried at 105°C. The yield of the dried coagulated solids was 170 g. The nature of the water solubles has not been investigated but qualitative tests showed it to contain reducing sugars and no starch.

Fat and resin.—The dried coagulated solids were extracted twice with acetone, under reflux, for 5 hours, the extract cooled and the solids filtered off. On distilling off acetone 100 g. of a transparent, balsam like, reddish brown, viscous fluid (acid value 2, saponification value 41.2) was obtained. Preliminary examination showed this to be a mixture of a fat and resins. Consequently the method as described below was adopted to effect their separation :—

Fat.—The viscous fluid (100 g.) was saponified with alcoholic sodium hydroxide as in the case of a fat. After the removal of alcohol by distillation, the saponified mass was taken up in hot water and the soapy solution was decomposed with concentrated hydrochloric acid to precipitate the mixed fatty acids and the resin acids along with neutral resins and unsaponifiable matter. These were removed while hot through a separating funnel and washed with hot water. The separated acid mother liquor and washings were made just alkaline and evaporated to dryness. The residue showed the presence of glycerol.

The mixture of the separated fatty acids, resin acids, neutral resins and unsaponifiable matter was neutralised with 25% sodium hydroxide, the resulting soap solution was incorporated with washed filter paper pulp and the whole mass thoroughly dried. It was then extracted with ethyl ether, in a soxhlet, to remove the unsaponifiables *i.e.*, all the resenes and the small amount of unsaponifiable matter. The residual soap was dissolved in water, the filter paper thoroughly squeezed and the total acids liberated with strong hydrochloric acid. These were washed, dried and filtered, the yield being 41 g. They were then separated into (a) solid acids, 6.7 g. (16.3%), (b) liquid acids, 31.4 g. (76.7%, Iodine value 92.5) and (c) resin acids 2.9 g. (7%) by Twitchell's method (Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

(a) The solid acids were fractionally crystallised from 95% alcohol. Two sets of fatty acid crystals were obtained, one melting at 80-81° (M. W. 369) and the other at 87°-88° (M.W. 400). These appeared to be lignoceric and cerotic acids, but were confirmed by their mixed melting points with pure lignoceric acid and pure cerotic acid respectively.

(b) The liquid acids when brominated in cold ether, according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch and Warburton; *Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fat and Waxes*, 1921, 6th Ed., Vol. I; 585) gave no precipitate of a hexabromide. The residue after evaporation of ether and crystallisation from petroleum ether yielded some crystals (m.p. 113°-114°) of linoleic tetrabromide. Isolation of this compound and the iodine value of the liquid acids show that they consist of oleic and linoleic acids.

(c) The resin acids were obtained in the form of their lead salts insoluble in boiling alcohol, in the Twitchell's separation. After decantation of the hot alcoholic solution of the salts of solid and liquid acids they were obtained by treating the residue with hot dilute hydrochloric acid. They were presumably derived from resin esters, associated with the fat and resin of the acetone extract.

Resin.—The ethereal solution of the unsaponifiables on distilling off the ether, yielded a brownish red, transparent, neutral resin (57 g.). It melted at 52°-54° and dissolved in almost all the organic solvents including petroleum ether. Its iodine value was 90.0. When distilled over sodium hydroxide at 200-250° it splits up into an aromatic distillate, $[\eta]_{25}^{25}$, 1.5103, and an acidic residue. None of these were further investigated.

Rubber.—The acetone insoluble portion (70 g.) was refluxed twice with 150 c.c. of chloroform for 2 hours and filtered. After distilling off chloroform from the filtrate the residue weighed 13.40 g. This was caoutchouc.

Protein, fibre etc.—The chloroform insoluble portion (56.6 g.) was a pink amorphous substance (acid value 10.4), insoluble in organic solvents. Salt solution dissolved a portion of it. Its nitrogen content was 11.2%. The major portion of the substance thus appeared to be protein and on the basis of its nitrogen content it contained 70% of proteinous matter and the balance 30% was crude fibre and inorganic matter. Being of no interest none of these products were investigated further.

Composition of the latex.—On the basis of the above data the chemical composition of the latex works out as follows:—

Water	62.0%	Water solubles	4.0%	Ash	1.7%	Fibre	2.7%
Proteins	7.9%	Fat and resin esters	8.6%	Resenes	21.4%	Rubber	27.7%